

FEATURES OF MARKETING ORGANIZATION IN THE MARKET OF CONSTRUCTION SERVICES

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Abstract. *This article is aimed at highlighting the specifics of organizing marketing activities in the construction industry. The authors focused on two aspects of marketing activities, namely, marketing services among market participants and segmentation of the construction market.*

Keywords: *investment construction industry, construction market participants, marketing service, market segmentation.*

Introduction. The approval of the 2021-2025 Strategy for the modernization, rapid and innovative development of the construction network of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan envisages a radical reform of marketing activities in this field. This strategy is one of the challenges facing the industry today. It is shown that the science of practical construction is underdeveloped. It is necessary to develop the scientific and methodological views of construction marketing in order to find full-fledged market relations in investment-construction processes.

Analysis of literature on the topic. There are several specific aspects related to the organization of marketing in construction practice, without taking into account it is difficult to talk about effective marketing activities. In theoretical developments, it is stated that the uniqueness of the construction market must first be connected to the properties of the construction product. Other scientists point to the complexity of organizational relations in the construction market as the main factor. In some construction industry marketing literature, it is proposed to divide this activity into external and internal marketing types. The development of the scientists of our country and the analysis of foreign literature show that there are many issues waiting to be solved in the organization of marketing activities in construction organizations.

It is necessary to pay respect to the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing in the economy, and the researches conducted in the field of economics in our country for many years were conducted on the basis of national characteristics. M. Muhammedov, M. Pardaev, R. Ibrohimov, Abdullaev Yu., Saliev A., Sharifkho'jaev M., Khodiev B., Rahimova D., Ergashkhojaeva Sh., Sh Musaeva and others are among them.

Research methodology. Solving this issue can be done by ensuring the priority of the needs of construction product consumers, the main principle of marketing methodology. The fact that the real consumer does not directly participate in the investment process requires additional research.

It is known that investment-construction processes are a comprehensive and multifaceted process, which is characterized by the large number of participants and the diversity of their interests. Investors, customers, designers, builders and users have different needs for construction products. In addition, the results of the investment-construction process will be of interest to many state, financial and market entities. In this regard, we believe that the nature of marketing in the

construction industry should be considered from the point of view of the participants' own interests.

Analysis and results. As a function of the market philosophy of marketing, the main interest of the investor is to ensure the target location of capital and the efficiency of the investment project. Based on this, the main content of marketing activities is to correctly assess the opportunities of the investment market and to find marketing solutions for capital allocation.

The customer, as a legal representative of the investor, must choose the most appropriate investment-construction scheme as a result of researching the construction market in order to protect his interests and carry out the necessary marketing activities to bring the project to a material object.

During the investment process, the project organization takes an active part in researching the market of architectural solutions and creating a construction object suitable for the customer in the materialization of the investment idea, and therefore focuses on the study of the properties of construction products in marketing activities.

The construction organization's marketing activity in the market is manifested in two main forms: meeting the needs of the customer and the designer, and maintaining and expanding its position in the market in the face of intense competition. In the first form, marketing activity is the basis for focusing production capabilities on the product, and in the second, it covers the sale and movement of construction products.

It can be seen that in the process of investment and construction, both marketing subjects and objects can have different appearances and can be interpreted differently. However, marketing is of particular importance for construction organizations, which are the most active participants in the construction market. Based on the above, the question arises as to what form and structures it is appropriate to organize marketing activities in construction organizations.

In our opinion, it is difficult to find a clear and firm answer to this question, because any enterprise has its own characteristics that make it stand out from others. [5] Together with this, we can give the following recommendations based on the specifics of the construction industry in general.

The organization of the marketing service should be consistent with the organization's market strategy and policy, that is, this service will not have any effect if it is created in the name of organizations;

Based on the experience of large foreign construction companies, the marketing service can be organized as part of the estimate-contract and sales department, or in the form of a separate marketing department. In this case, the marketing department serves to organize work with customers in a comprehensive way. Such an independently formed service takes into account only the interests of this firm. At the same time, this type of structure has a special place and becomes an integral part of the organization from the functional point of view, and leads to an increase in administrative costs.

Organizations that are financially vulnerable to market research and marketing strategy in the construction industry also play a major role. In such organizations, the cost of extensive marketing services can harm economic stability. In this regard, in our opinion, the following two organizational forms can be used: integrated marketing structures and external specialized marketing services. It is advisable to organize integrated marketing structures under construction associations or regional engineering companies. In the first case, the marketing structure is inter-

organizational, and in the second case, it functions as a vertical marketing structure of a single customer. The lack of development of such structures in Uzbekistan is due to the fact that the value of marketing information is decreasing as a result of being confined within one organization. Indeed, no matter how large a construction organization is, it cannot cover the entire market, and the requirements for marketing information will not be met.

Today, outside specialized marketing services are widespread in the construction industry, as in all industries. In such an organizational form, the organization of marketing activities in construction organizations is entrusted to independent specialized firms on the basis of a contract. Independent consulting firms can provide services related to all areas of marketing without distracting the construction organization from its core activities. Consulting firms can provide information to all construction market participants. In contrast to the consumer market, such a situation may not cause harm, but on the contrary, it can give a positive result. At the same time, the leader of the construction organization will have high-quality marketing information, and the organizational structure will be oriented towards production.

An important feature of marketing activities in the construction industry is related to market segmentation. It is appropriate to consider separately the concept of the construction market based on the actions of consumers and their representatives.

The construction market is understood as the branch of the economy related to the direction of investments in the capital sector and their development. In its research, the main attention is paid to the implementation of construction works and the operation of facilities.

On the other hand, market segmentation serves the specialization of construction organizations and market branching. A single approach to construction market segmentation has not been developed. As an example, it will be possible to distinguish the signs of segmentation of the construction market at the national level based on the state statistics in the field of investment and construction. A number of signs of segmentation of the construction market are related to construction and assembly work (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Signs of segmentation of the construction work market at the country level.

The first sign of segmentation divides the participants of the construction ordering market: large and small organizations on the basis of a contract and independently (informal sector). In 2023, 24,239.4 billion soums of total construction works were completed by large contracting organizations, the share of the total construction works was 27.6%, and the contribution of small enterprises and micro-firms was 52.8% of the total construction works. or 46371.0 billion som. The contribution of the informal sector was 19.6% or 17213.5 billion soums of construction and assembly works. The situation in the construction market is shown by the division of construction objects by function, that is, non-residential, i.e., production objects, residential and public or civil objects, and specialized construction works. 73.2% - 64,287.0 billion were spent in the

development of construction projects, construction of non-residential buildings and structures in our country, 15.1% - 13,261.4 billion in the construction of civil construction objects. billion soums, 11.7% - 10,275.4 billion soums were completed in specialized construction works. 3,652.0 billion soums or 4.2% of the total construction works by state organizations, and 84,171.8 billion soums or total by non-governmental organizations 95.8% of works have been completed.

When segmenting the construction market on the basis of statistical data, great attention is paid to the indication of geographical location, because it will be possible to determine in which area the investments and construction products are distributed more. For example, if we analyze the construction and assembly works completed by the end of 2023 by region, the region with the largest share is the city of Tashkent (18,758.9 billion soums), followed by Tashkent (6,930.6 billion soums), Samarkand (5665.9 billion soums) and Bukhara (5387.2 billion soums) regions are the most attractive construction segment.

Based on the territorial construction market and the interests of separate organizations, the following symbols are also used to segment the market: construction, assembly and adjustment, repair works; general contracting and subcontracting works; segmentation of buildings by functionality (residences, public buildings, industrial buildings, etc.); project, search, general construction, special construction works; construction of separate objects and complexes, etc. Therefore, it is appropriate to use the above signs when organizing marketing activities in the investment-construction market, studying the macro environment, and segmenting the market.

Conclusions and suggestions. Taking into account that marketing makes it possible to have perfect information about the construction market, it is proposed to apply its principles widely. Only the marketing information system allows the construction organization to see the state of the market, therefore, marketing should be used to classify existing and potential customers, find new solutions regarding the properties of project organizations and objects, distinguish important quality marks of construction products. In addition, the role of marketing knowledge and methods is invaluable in developing an optimal pricing policy at a time when the construction pricing system is changing. Based on this, the development of external marketing services in the construction industry is becoming an important issue of the industry.

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